

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Toshova Zulfizar zulfiqor qizi

IS'HOQON TO'RA IBRAT HAYOTI VA ILMIY MEROSI. LUG'AT

SITTA "AL-SINA" ASARI BADIY TAHLILI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

